

AN INSIGHT TO WHITE COLLAR CRIMES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The conception of white-collar crime lacks a precise and universally accepted definition, necessitating criminologists to conduct individual analyses and interpretations. The Indian Penal Code of 1860 forms the legal framework for addressing such crimes, which encompasses a wide range of offenses within administrative and professional domains. This type of crime includes occupational, organizational, and various fraudulent activities perpetrated by individuals in positions of authority. High-profile cases like the Satyam Scandal underscore the urgent need for proactive measures to combat such malfeasance, necessitating collaboration between government bodies, law enforcement agencies, regulatory authorities, and corporate entities. Weak internal controls, lack of oversight, and technological advancements contribute to the proliferation of fraudulent activities, posing significant challenges for both public and private sectors. This review article comprehensively examines the landscape of white-collar crimes in India, addressing its definitions, classifications, and notable case studies. It also addresses proactive measures such as whistle-blowing, forensic accounting, enhanced audit, and control mechanisms, along with initiatives taken by the Indian government under the Honourable Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi to control and prevent fraud in various financial sectors to safeguard India's economic and social fabric.

Keywords: Crime, White-collar crime, Indian Penal Code, Occupational Crime, Organizational Crime, Proactive measures, Government initiatives, financial sector fraud prevention

1. INTRODUCTION

In sociological terms, crime refers any act that is not appropriate as per societal laws, can be done for personal or public agenda, and which can or cannot harm someone. Deviance against social norms can be observed in various domains such as education, politics, social interactions, and religious practices. It is important to note that deviance is both context-specific and influenced by the religious beliefs and social customs of crime victims. (Sharma, 1974; S. S. Simpson, 2010; Smith et al., 2010; Sutherland, 1983).

There are different types of criminal activities, and one significant type is white-collar crime. The Indian Penal Code of 1860 is the latest and most extensive law concerning crime in India. It covers various offenses related to administrative and professional environments. These offenses involve bribery, corruption, counterfeiting, violations of standards, corruption in industries like food and pharmaceuticals, misuse of property, breach of trust, fraud, forgery, falsification, and financial dishonesty

There are three main factors that contribute to employees' propensity to participate in white-collar crime. These include availability of the opportunities to commit such crimes, situational and personal pressures faced by workers, and issues related to integrity and honesty (S. Simpson, 2009, Weisburd, 2009).

These crimes are more complex and need careful planning. The people who commit white-collar crimes are not like typical criminals. They tend to target organizations instead of individuals. White-collar criminals often have jobs, are well-educated, and usually do not have a history of being in trouble with the law (Sagar, 2019).

Middle-class wrong doings have become a pressing global issue that is rapidly escalating. Numerous investigations have exposed the fact that the financial harm inflicted by middle-class misconduct on the general population surpasses that caused by other offenses. In the case of India, a non-industrial nation, middle-class wrongdoings not only impede economic progress but also tarnish the country's reputation. While eliminating middle-class misbehaviour may seem like an insurmountable task, it is crucial for us, along with government and legal entities, to exert every effort to reduce such infractions. The implementation of stringent regulations and the establishment of specialized bodies are necessary to in still fear of punishment among wrongdoers and prompt them to reconsider their actions before engaging in any criminal activity. Additionally, it is imperative for the government and relevant organizations to collaborate diligently in eradicating such wrongdoings from our nation (Gorasiya & Chudasama, 2021).

Occupational crimes exhibit a distinction from conventional street crimes as they are committed by individuals entrusted

with positions of authority and responsibility. For instance, medical fraud is typically carried out exclusively by physicians, while bank embezzlement is commonly committed by trusted bank personnel. The driving force behind occupational criminals is fundamentally like that of street criminals: the desire to swiftly attain rewards with minimal exertion (Clinard, 1952; Gottschalk, 2018; Green, 1993; Levi, 2013; UPADHYAY, 2014). Distinguishing between corporate offenses and criminal acts committed by employees or small businesses, as well as categorizing crimes against companies, crimes by corporations, and criminal corporations, can be misleading because each category can encompass a broad range of offenses. When attempting to explain crime based on market variables, it is important to recognize that these factors can have diverse impacts on different groups of offenders within the same offense category. The influence and ability of large firms to manipulate laws and bypass legal restrictions may contribute to a rise in small-business crime due to the economic difficulties associated with a recession (Croall, 1989; Grabosky et al., 1987; Minkes & Minkes, 2008; Pontell & Geis, 2007).

When examining arrests related to white-collar crime in comparison to arrests in other datasets, an important aspect to consider is whether they are capturing equivalent phenomena. It is possible that the implications of an arrest for white collar crime differ from those for a street crime. In instances of white-collar crime, it is generally the prosecutors, rather than the police, who assume the role of primary investigators. White-collar crimes are often more complex to disentangle and frequently lack clearly identifiable victims (Gottschalk, 2011; Kawasaki, 2019; Weisburd et al., 2001).

The General Strain Theory (GST) examines different aspects of white-collar crime, including professional offenses committed by wealthy individuals, specific economic violations like fraud and embezzlement, typically perpetrated by people from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, and corporate crimes. Some strain theorists and scholars suggest that these crimes become more common when individuals cannot attain their economic goals through lawful methods (Agnew et al., 2009).

2. Types of white-collar crime

According to general perception, white-collar crimes are classified into 2 main domains: Occupational Crime and Organizational Crime. Different types of widely recognized types of white-collar crimes, such as:

Banking & financial fraud is done by participating in activities or conduct with the deliberate aim to deceive a bank for personal gain. Individuals involved in financial wrongdoing have exploited their connections with bank administrations, targeting both nationalized and cooperative banks and diverting substantial funds. The burden of non-performing

assets in nationalized banks largely falls on these influential borrowers. In the 1990s, corrupt financial wrongdoers established Urban Cooperative Banks (UCBs) in Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Gujarat, accumulating significant funds by promising unrealistically high returns. Subsequently, they diverted these funds by granting loans to themselves or individuals linked to them through illicit networks. Such institutions would typically collapse, leading to the loss of many small investors (Gorasiya & Chudasama, 2021; Spalek, 2001; UPADHYAY, 2014; Yallapragada et al., 2012).

Blackmail is demanding money under the threat of physical harm, property damage, or exposure of secrets (Lindgren, 1984).

As per Section 171 E of the Indian Penal Code (IPC), bribery encompasses the act of offering financial incentives, commodities, services, or privileged information with the objective of exerting influence on the actions, opinions, or decisions of the recipient (Indian Penal Code, 1860).

Cellular phone fraud signifies the unauthorized usage, tampering, or manipulation of cellular phone services (Ibrahim et al., 2015).

Embezzlement pertains to the misappropriation of funds or assets by an individual who was entrusted with them, with the intention of benefiting personally (UPADHYAY, 2014).

Counterfeiting is an act of replicating or imitating something without authorization. A significant inflow of counterfeit money can devastate an economy and compromise public safety in any country. This issue has a long history in India, but with advancements in technology, high-quality counterfeit currency notes have been discovered in the possession of terrorists coming from across the border. Counterfeit money primarily enters India through Nepal and Dubai. In addition to large quantities of counterfeit currency being smuggled into the country, criminal gangs and individuals within India are utilizing computers and sophisticated printers to produce counterfeit money notes. Considering its repercussions on both domestic and global platforms, it is imperative for the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI), and state law enforcement agencies to undertake necessary measures (Gorasiya & Chudasama, 2021; UPADHYAY, 2014).

Forgery involves the deliberate act of circulating fabricated or worthless documents, such as counterfeit securities or forged checks, with the intent to deceive and perpetrate fraud (Diab, 1972; Nickell, 2005).

Tax Evasion is frequently utilized by the middle-class to acquire undisclosed funds. Organized crime is closely linked to illegal tax evasion. Tax evasion involves the process of giving the appearance that a large sum of money, acquired through illegal means such as drug sales or terrorism, originates from a legitimate source. Essentially, it is the transformation of illicit "black" money into "white" money, allowing criminals to legitimize their unlawfully obtained wealth. The objective is to clean and reintroduce the significant cash

amounts into circulation. When carried out effectively, it allows perpetrators to maintain authority over their unlawful profits and ultimately create an outwardly lawful appearance for their illicit earnings (Saxena, 2021; Singh & Bagchi, 2018).

Adulteration is an intentional practice of introducing impurities, substandard components, or deceitful modifications into goods, usually with the aim of misleading consumers, compromising the quality, or obtaining unfair economic benefits (Bansal et al., 2017; Beniwal & Khetarpaul, 1999; Gawande & Kaware, 2013).

Insurance Frauds by insurance companies have become victims of fraudulent claimants, with or without the involvement of corrupt insurance authorities. Common practices include intentionally setting fire to insured properties, warehouses, and production lines, filing multiple claims for the same incident, and inflated claims supported by dishonest assessors (Gorasiya & Chudasama, 2021).

Money laundering involves individuals who consciously aim to profit from, actively aid, or participate in any endeavour linked to the proceeds of illegal activities, thereby perpetuating its transformation into legitimate assets, can face legal charges for money laundering. Money laundering has detrimental effects on a country's economy and political stability, making it crucial for strict monitoring and collective action by governments worldwide (Gorasiya & Chudasama, 2021). The acts of hoarding and profiteering stand out as significant forms of white-collar crimes frequently observed within the field of commerce and business in India. The government of India has implemented a range of regulatory laws, and any contravention of these statutes is deemed as a white-collar crime (Gorasiya & Chudasama, 2021; Petter Gottschalk, 2011).

3. White collar crime & fraud in India

The findings from Kroll's 2010-2011 Annual Global Fraud Survey, carried out by the Economist Intelligence Unit, are consistent with expectations. Fraud continues to pose a major global challenge, with India being significantly affected. The survey reveals that 75 percent of organizations surveyed reported encountering fraud. In India specifically, 84 percent of businesses admitted to being victims of fraudulent activities (Nagarajan & Sheriff, 2012; Pontell & Geis, 2014).

A report highlights a concerning reality: most instances of fraud originate from individuals within the company or with connections to it. Globally, insiders accounted for 60% of fraud cases, with 28% involving junior employees, 21% involving senior employees, and 11% involving third-party agents. In India, 59% of frauds were committed by insiders. Frauds perpetrated by senior employees pose significant risks to companies, leading to substantial financial losses

and damage to reputation. Despite this, many Indian companies still do not prioritize internal controls and management oversight. However, the government has taken some steps to address the high levels of fraud in the Indian private sector. Empowering the Serious Fraud Investigation Office (SFIO) through the new Companies Bill is seen as a positive step. SFIO will have increased authority to conduct investigations, make arrests, carry out raids, and seize assets. These measures could potentially curb the growing number of financial fraud cases in India (Nagarajan & Sheriff, 2012). The second India Fraud Survey conducted in August-September 2021 aimed to figure out the types of fraud that companies in India face, the main risks they are exposed to, and what causes fraudulent behavior. The survey found that weak internal controls were the main reason for fraud, according to about half of the respondents. They also pointed out that lack of oversight contributes to fraud. Losing confidential data was another big worry, mentioned by over half of the respondents.

The impact of fraud seemed to be connected to the size of the company, with larger businesses possibly facing more damage to their reputation (CII-Kroll India Fraud Survey, 2021).

To sustain the economic progress, India needs to effectively eliminate fraudulent activities and corruption in both public and private sectors. Corruption and fraudulent practices create barriers for companies considering investments in the country. The decrease in foreign direct investment seen in 2011 and the withdrawal of capital from stock markets by international financial institutions are clear signs of the negative impact of fraud and corruption (Headworth et al., 2016; Nagarajan & Sheriff, 2012).

The rise in white-collar crime in recent years is often linked to rapid economic growth and industrial expansion. Reports like the Santhanam Committee Report shed light on crimes committed by individuals of higher social status, such as businessmen, industrialists, contractors, suppliers, and corrupt public officials. Investigations by commissions like the Vivin Bose Commission of Inquiry, examining the activities of the Dalmia Jain group of companies in 1963, reveal how industrialists frequently engage in white-collar crimes like forgery, fraud, falsifying accounts, tampering with records, and tax evasion for personal gain. Similar findings were noted by Honourable Justice M.C. Chagla in the case of business magnate Mundhra, who aimed to build an industrial empire through questionable means. Notable scandals like the Satyam scam, Vijay Mallya's flight, and the 2G scams prompted the Government of India to pass the Fugitive Economic Offenders Act in 2018. Technological advancements, especially in the late 20th century, have opened up new avenues for white-collar crimes. According to recent trends, the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) reported 6,533 corruption cases over the past decade, resulting in 517 convictions. Data also shows fraudulent trading worth 4,000 crores using fake PAN cards and a rise in online crime cases in Maharashtra. Approximately 3.2 million people have fallen victim to card details theft from bank ATMs. These concerning statistics underscore the prevalence of white-collar crimes in India (Indian National Bar Association, 2019).

The widespread adoption of cryptocurrencies, characterized by their decentralized and anonymous nature, has led to numerous adverse effects on both society and the economy. This appealing aspect of cryptocurrencies has attracted the attention of fraudsters and scammers, who exploits the lack of stringent regulations and the anonymity of transac-

Fig. 1 According to (Nagarajan & Sheriff, 2012) the global level and India share the same top six categories of fraud.

tions to perpetrate various scams, Ponzi schemes, and deceptive Initial Coin Offerings (ICOs), resulting in significant financial losses for unsuspecting investors. The anonymity offered by cryptocurrencies, expedited illegal activities such as money laundering, posing significant challenges for law enforcement agencies in tracking and combating such criminal activities. This challenge is further exacerbated by the existence of the dark web, where stolen data from millions of internet users worldwide, including approximately 600,000 individuals from India, is traded using automated bots at very low cost which represents serious implications for cybersecurity. A recent ransomware attack targeting the All-India Institute of Medical Sciences in Delhi serves as a stark example, causing substantial disruptions to its cyber infrastructure. This signifies the interconnected nature of these technologies and underscores the urgent need for collaborative efforts, clear regulatory frameworks, and enhanced public awareness to effectively address these challenges and ensure responsible integration for the collective benefit of society (Mukherjee et al., 2024; Verma et al., 2023).

4. Wrong-perceptions about white-collar crime

First myth is that white-collar crime is peaceful - This misunderstanding stem from the belief that white-collar crime is typically devoid of violence. However, offenders frequently demonstrate a sense of entitlement and a craving for influence. Second common misconception is that white-collar criminals are highly paid individuals. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that they often take advantage of low-wage workers as part of their fraudulent schemes. Third myth is that white-collar criminals are otherwise upstanding individuals - Contrary to popular belief, approximately 40% of white-collar offenders have a criminal history. Fourth myth is that it is all about the money. While some white-collar criminals may be financially strained, the orchestrators of these crimes can be quite affluent. Based on studies conducted by researchers, elements such as peer influence, corporate environment, and excessive hubris play a significant role in the perpetration of white-collar crimes (Nagarajan & Sheriff, 2012).

5. Case Studies:

5.1. Case Study 1

The Sahara India Real Estate Corporation Ltd. (SIRECL) and the Sahara Housing Investment Corporation Ltd. (SHICL) were embroiled in a legal dispute with the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI).

“In 2008-2009, the Company raised a fully convertible debenture worth Rs 24,400 crores to merge SIRECL and SHICL. The recipients of this agreement were individuals associated or affiliated in any way with the Sahara India Group of

Companies, including friends, partners, group organizations, employees, and others. The total number of recipients exceeded 2.21 crores, and their addresses remained unknown. No fictitious accounts were created, and the debenture was handed over to innocent financial supporters. However, on August 31, 2012, the Honourable Supreme Court delivered its final verdict. The ruling against Sahara mandates that the two companies must pay the accumulated amount, which is Rs 24,400 crores plus 15% interest, to their 2.21 crore financial supporters.” (Gorasiya & Chudasama, 2021).

5.2. Case Study 2

Satyam Computer Services Limited, established by Mr. Ramalinga Raju in Hyderabad in 1987, was a prosperous Indian IT-services company. With an initial workforce of just 20 individuals, the organization experienced swift expansion and evolved into a worldwide enterprise providing IT and BPO services across diverse industries. Satyam garnered a reputation for its ingenuity, effective management practices, and commitment to corporate responsibility, receiving accolades like Ernst & Young’s prestigious “Entrepreneur of the Year” award in 2007 and the esteemed “Global Peacock Award” for outstanding global corporate accountability from the World Council for Corporate Governance in September 2008. Regrettably, in a span of less than five months following the attainment of the honour, Satyam was unveiled to be involved in an extensive accounting fraud of significant proportions.

In a correspondence addressed to the Board of Directors of Satyam Computers Limited on January 7, 2009, Mr. Raju confessed to orchestrating the manipulation of the company’s financial figures over a span of several years. Through manipulation, the company artificially increased the worth of its assets by a staggering \$1.47 billion, out of which \$1.04 billion were fictitious bank loans and cash, while at the same time deliberately concealing or underestimating its liabilities. The company also inflated its income in nearly every quarter to meet analyst expectations. To carry out the fraudulent scheme, Mr. Raju utilized his personal computer to fabricate counterfeit bank statements, manipulate bank records, and artificially boost income statements by falsely asserting interest income from fictitious bank accounts. Furthermore, he established 6,000 fictitious salary accounts and misappropriated the funds deposited by the company. The complicity of the company’s global head of internal audit was also evident as they engaged in fabricating customer identities, generating fraudulent invoices, forging board resolutions, and illicitly securing loans on behalf of the company. Additionally, the cash raised through American Depository Receipts in the United States was intentionally omitted from the balance sheets (Bhasin, 2013).

Several other significant white-collar crimes have occurred in India. Suresh Chandrasekhar, orchestrated scams involv-

ing influential figures, amassing millions. Sudipto Sen's Saradha Chit Fund fraud lured rural investors with false promises, collecting 300 billion rupees before collapse, leading to legal actions and a relief fund. Harshad Mehta's stock manipulation scam earned him over 5000 crore rupees, causing panic selling and prompting SEBI reforms. These cases highlight the impact and complexity of white-collar crimes in India (Kaushik et al., n.d.).

6. Proactive measures

Whistleblowing plays a crucial role in uncovering many white-collar crimes that are later prosecuted. Policing financial crime involves various elements such as detection processes, the responsibilities of shareholders, CEOs, senior executives, investigations, and forensic analysis, with whistleblowers being central to this process. They act as both a source of suspicion and evidence. However, caution is advised when choosing whom to disclose information to, as there is a risk that the recipient may be involved in the illicit activities (Eaton & Weber, 2008).

The application of forensic accounting presents an effective approach for examining fraudulent behaviors, particularly within financial crimes. The effectiveness of forensic accounting lies in its ability to uncover fraud, which often involves obtaining assets or financial gains through deceptive tactics like altering or hiding information. Forensic investigations analyze digital evidence, including different forms of communication. Additionally, accounting plays a vital role in conducting audits and implementing measures to prevent white-collar crime (Curtis, 2008; Kaur & Mukherjee, 2023). The government of India, led by Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi, has implemented several measures to combat and prevent fraud in the financial sectors. One significant step is the issuance of a "Framework for timely detection, reporting, investigation relating to large value bank frauds" to Public Sector Banks (PSBs). This framework mandates the examination of accounts exceeding fifty crores' rupees classified as Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) for potential fraud, with findings reported to the bank's Committee for Review of NPAs. Moreover, wilful default cases are promptly investigated upon fraud reporting to the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), and borrower reports are obtained from the Central Economic Intelligence Bureau for NPAs. The Fugitive Economic Offenders Act, 2018 aims to dissuade economic offenders from evading Indian law by seizing their property and disqualifying them from defending civil claims. The establishment of the Central Fraud Registry (CFR) by RBI provides a searchable online database to monitor fraud, while the initiation of the National Financial Reporting Authority ensures the enforcement of auditing standards and audit quality (Press Information Bureau Government of India Ministry of Finance, 2018).

The government is preparing to enact various strategies

aimed at addressing the escalating issue of cyber fraud within the financial sector. Among these measures are proposals to restrict access to the unique mobile device identifier (IMEI) and to enforce limitations on withdrawals from suspicious accounts to mitigate the potential for misuse in subsequent incidents (The Economic Times, 2023).

7. Conclusion

White-collar crime, with its complex nature and far-reaching consequences, remains a significant challenge for societies, particularly in rapidly developing economies like India. This review article has provided a comprehensive examination of various aspects of white-collar crime, ranging from its definitions and classifications to notable case studies and proactive measures for prevention. The Indian Penal Code of 1860 delimits provisions addressing professional misconduct, reflecting the evolving landscape of criminal activities within administrative and professional settings. Despite lacking a precise and generalized definition, white-collar crime encompasses a wide range of offenses, including occupational and organizational crimes, as well as a multitudinous fraudulent activities perpetrated by individuals in positions of authority. The pervasiveness of white-collar crime in India, underscored by high-profile cases such as the Satyam Scandal and Sahara India legal dispute, highlights the urgent need for proactive measures to combat such malfeasance. Weak internal controls, lack of oversight, and technological advancements have contributed to the proliferation of fraudulent activities, posing significant challenges for both public and private sectors. That is why, addressing white-collar crime in India requires a multi-faceted approach involving collaboration between government bodies, law enforcement agencies, regulatory authorities, and corporate entities. By the implementation of various government initiatives and proactive measures such as whistle-blowing, forensic accounting, and enhanced audit and control mechanisms and strengthening a culture of integrity and ethical conduct, India can alleviate the detrimental impact of white-collar crime and safeguard its economic and social fabric for the future generations.

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